

INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES USING MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article is about innovative methods of teaching and learning foreign languages. The article focuses on the use of innovation in education to explore research and use all the tools to uncover something new. A different way of looking at problems and solving them are given in this article . The thinking process that goes into it will help students develop their creativity and their problem solving skills.

Keywords : competence, foreign language, learning process, innovative methods.

At the present time, innovations in education encourage teachers and students to work more on themselves, explore and use all the tools to discover something new in education. This suggests a different way of looking at problems and their solutions. The thinking process that is included in it will help students develop their creativity and problem-solving skills. As the modern world undergoes changes and developments, you can see that innovations are being introduced in all areas, as well as in education. The key to learning is teaching and learning. Innovative methods in teaching and learning can affect many industries such as economics, medicine and politics. Education is a catalyst for development. It is impossible to succeed without sufficient knowledge.

Innovative teaching methods mean organizing lessons using new perspectives and non-traditional forms of learning. These methods and forms of learning play the role of activities that make students enthusiastic about the lesson. One of the most fascinating and noticeable methods is the dispute method. In the debate method, it is important to create a friendly atmosphere in the audience, because each participant must interact with others and solve problems with inspiration. This method will improve the skills of expressing ideas in another foreign language. If students do not practice speaking from time to time, their period of study may be longer than those who constantly work on themselves. Such students need to improve their skills, practice more and hone their skills. The debate method is useful because it also develops public speaking skills. At times it can be difficult to express ideas in front of an audience, even in one's own language. Thus, the dispute method improves speech impact and oratory skills. During the discussion, the

teacher should divide students into groups, thus giving them the opportunity to improve their speaking and other skills, helping and supporting each other.

Such innovative teaching methods give effective results when there is feedback between the teacher and the student. Innovation in learning is designed to solve problems and enhance social values. They provide new solutions and remove traditional barriers to existing, articulated problems in teaching and learning.

This teaching method teaches students to work on mistakes and learn from their own experience. Students can practice their language skills by interacting with native speakers such as tourists, foreigners and study friends. Consequently, they can speak with native speakers and improve their speaking and listening skills. Students can guide foreigners and show them the places they need or suggest other places of interest. During the conversation, they can give interesting data about their hometown and at the same time learn about interesting facts from the interlocutor. This method of learning a language is not only useful, but also interesting.

By generalizing knowledge, students develop their ideas together with others and develop the ability to think in a foreign language. This process is intensive. The motivation is that during the debate, students learn to quickly express their thoughts. Namely, students who learn English are able to think in this language and communicate their thoughts and ideas to others associatively. This method gives them the opportunity to improve not only the language they learn, but also their thinking abilities. During judgments and discourses, students learn to listen to each other, actively and constructively respond to others. In this stage, students learn to stand up for their opinions and treat others with respect. For example, if students are given a discussion topic “What is your opinion about the credit system of education in your country?”, then the first thing the student does is listen carefully to the ideas of others, and only then he gives out his thoughts and ideas on this issue. From this it follows that he generates answers and tries to use his vocabulary by matching. In this way, the student learns to interpret the topic given to him, carefully explain his thoughts and ideas, and listen to the opinions of others, despite the opposite and contradictory opinions of others. This is a useful side of the innovative method of dispute in teaching.

Each existing method has its positive and negative sides. The advantages are that new pedagogical technologies and modern science make students independent learners. In other words, they can use Internet resources such as e-books, as well as applications for learning information. Modern technologies such as smartphones, computers, tablets give them unlimited access to the Internet. There are many e-books on the Internet and of course they have their advantages. There are various libraries in higher education institutions, but if all students need to use textbooks at the same time, there will not be enough of them, and students will have to wait a long time. However, they can download their electronic versions from the Internet, and this will be enough for them.

Currently, the use of the Internet and modern technologies is the most advanced type in obtaining knowledge through online lessons existing in the network space. The younger generation receives information from Internet resources, while they do not look for reliable primary sources, but rely on publicly available data. They need to get knowledge in educational institutions in the real world and develop social skills. In many countries, children still continue to use gadgets and other modern technologies for games and entertainment, thus wasting their time. They prefer to play games or watch movies on digital devices rather than read e-books or learn how to write programs or work with computer applications. After all, it is most effective to use gadgets for learning foreign languages. What's more, with these high-tech devices, the younger generation can develop their skills by using numerous foreign language learning apps. As for students studying English in higher education, they have their own concepts on many issues. Students use modern technologies and gadgets mainly for the development of independent work and projects in areas. However, using Internet resources, students get used to getting information in an easy way, which eventually leads to plagiarism. Students should understand that high technology was invented by man through scientific knowledge.

In many countries, higher education institutions are equipped with modern technologies in order to develop the education system. In our country, special attention is paid to equipping classrooms with modern high-tech devices, but, like everywhere else, there are shortcomings that need to be eliminated in the coming years and create alternative uses for multimedia technologies.

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